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OBJECTIVE

To compare the proportion of people with positive alpha-synuclein (aSyn) aggregation, detected by seed amplification assay (SAA), among groups with differing levels of certainty of REM sleep behavior disorder (RBD).

BACKGROUND

RBD is a parasomnia defined by dream enactment behavior (DEB) and absence of atonia during REM sleep on polysomnogram (PSG). PSG-confirmed RBD is a specific feature of early alpha-synucleinopathy, but PSG is not practical for large-scale screening. DEB is commonly reported, but only a subset have RBD. Accurate yet scalable methods to identify people with DEB with aSyn pathology are needed.

METHODS

PPMI participants included in this analysis were either

- (1) Identified by clinical sites as PSG-confirmed RBD (RBD-PSG) or
 - (2) a. Self-reported an RBD or DEB through an online questionnaire
 b. Hyposmic, defined by University of Pennsylvania Smell Identification Test (UPSIT) score <10th percentile
 c. At least mildly abnormal DAT-SPECT, defined by lowest putamen specific binding ratio [SBR] <100% expected for age and sex
- Cerebrospinal fluid aSyn-SAA through Amprion was conducted and baseline clinical measures compared.

RESULTS

As of January 2024, 450 participants with either RBD-PSG (n = 240), self-reported RBD with hyposmia (RBD+Hypos; n = 74), or no diagnosis of RBD but DEB with hyposmia (DEB+Hypos; n = 136) were enrolled. More RBD+Hypos and DEB+Hypos had positive aSyn SAA compared to RBD-PSG. When RBD-PSG were limited to UPSIT < 10th %ile and mSBR < 100 % (n = 139), a similar proportion had positive aSyn SAA.

Mean (SD) or n (%)	RBD-PSG N = 240	DEB+Hypos N=136	RBD+Hypos N=74
Age	67.6 (6.3)	68.6 (5.6)	69.3 (5.5)
Female	51 (21%)	63 (46%)	19 (26%)
UPSIT %ile	14.7 (15.5)	4.5 (2.4)	4.5 (2.4)
SBR % Expected	80.5 (25.9)	67.8 (20.9)	67.0 (17.8)
aSyn SAA*			
Type 1	171 (71%)	114 (84%)	66 (89%)
Type 2	2 (1%)	0	0
Negative	67 (28%)	22 (16%)	8 (11%)

*Type 1 signal (high fluorescence) is predominantly found in neuronal synuclein disease, and Type 2 signal (low fluorescence) in patients with glial cytoplasmic inclusions and/or clinical presentations of MSA.

Mean (SD) or n (%)	RBD-PSG UPSIT ≥ 10 th %ile N = 101	RBD-PSG, UPSIT < 10 th %ile N = 139
Age	67.5 (5.7)	67.7 (6.8)
Female	23 (23%)	28 (20%)
UPSIT %ile	28.2 (15.8)	4.9 (2.4)
SBR % Expected	82.9 (23.7)	78.7 (27.2)
aSyn SAA		
Type 1	43 (43%)	128 (92%)
Type 2	2 (1%)	0
Negative	56 (55%)	56 (55%)

Figure 1: Distribution of DAT-SPECT results and UPSIT results among people with RBD-PSG only.

	RBD-PSG < 10th %ile N=128	iRBD ≥ 10th %ile N=43	RBD-Hypos N=66	DEB-Hypos N=114
MDS-UPDRS:				
Part I	7.7 (5.6)	7.7 (4.5)	8.7 (5.2)	8.0 (4.9)
Part II	2.0 (2.9)	2.2 (3.1)	2.7 (3.5)	2.6 (3.2)
Part III	4.3 (4.9)	4.3 (6.1)	5.7 (5.4)	6.3 (6.1)
Total	14.0 (9.9)	14.3 (10.4)	17.0 (10.5)	16.7 (10.6)
RBDSQ	9.9 (2.4)	10.4 (2.7)	10.4 (2.3)	8.1 (3.0)
SCOPA-AUT	12.7 (6.5)	11.1 (5.4)	13.1 (6.5)	12.0 (6.4)
MoCA	26.4 (2.5)	26.6 (2.8)	26.5 (2.4)	26.8 (2.1)

CONCLUSION

Questionnaires followed by smell testing may be a scalable way to identify people with synucleinopathy. Mild DAT-SPECT abnormality was required for our screening protocol but appears less important than UPSIT when enriching for people with positive aSyn-SAA, at least among the RBD-PSG group.

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